

JAIN STATUARY FROM DHAR AND MANDU IN MADHYA PRADESH

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Several stone statues of Jain tīrthaṅkaras from the Paramāra kingdom of Malwa (972-1305) are preserved in the state archaeological museums of Dhar and Mandu in Madhya Pradesh. They survive in various states of damage that preclude a full assessment of their art historical context. However, some statues bear iconographic elements of identification and dedicatory inscriptions rich in information about patronage. Most of these Sanskrit inscriptions have been noticed in the *Annual Report on Indian Epigraphy* (ARIE) but are deciphered and translated here for the first time.

A group of eighteen Jain statues are on display at the archaeological museum of Dhar, located inside the Fort premises since 2010, under the Directorate of Archaeology, Museums and Archives of Madhya Pradesh. This collection began with images unearthed in the City Palace of the Pawar kings in 1875 and preserved in the former Department of History and Museum.¹ Ten statues belong to Dhar while eight belong to Salkanpur, 11 km south-east of Dhar just off the royal road leading to Mandu, vide Survey of India map sheet no. 46N6. Three more statues from Salkanpur are displayed at the state archaeological museum of Mandu, located in the Chhappan Mahal. A passing visit to Salkanpur in 2020 did not yield any ruins of temples where these eleven images may have come from, but remains of several Brahmanical sculptures were found next to an old reservoir with a stepped bank of well-dressed stone masonry and image niches dating from the Paramāra period.² Among the best-preserved statues is one from Mandu, displayed in the ASI museum at Taveli Mahal. In what follows, this corpus of twenty-two statues is presented in a chronological sequence established through stylistic and epigraphic analysis.

* This paper is based on fieldwork carried out in December 2018. We thank Alaas Khan and Anne Casile for providing fresh photos of some of the sculptures.

¹ Lele 1944: iii.

² Salkanpur is missing from the list of archaeological sites first reported in Luard 1908: 509, and more inventoried in Sharma 1998.

Three Śvetāmbara Statues from Dhar

Among the most remarkable statues from Dhar – rivaling in quality the famous sculpture of the Jain goddess Ambikā dated 1034 in Bhoja’s reign (c. 1010-1055) and now preserved in the British Museum – are three seated images of tīrthaṅkaras (**figs. 1-3**).³ They are all carved from marble blocks enlivened by veins and finished to a high polish. Although devoid of an inscription like the one borne by Ambikā, the tīrthaṅkaras also belong to the Śvetāmbara denomination, as indicated by a loin cloth on the waist and its frilled end visible under the folded feet. The three figures have slender bodies with sloping shoulders and a narrow waist tapering to rounded hips, reminiscent of the delicately modeled volumes of Ambikā. A sober style is suggested by the subtle contrast between smooth areas of flesh and the low-relief decoration of the cushions, pectoral jewels, hail curls, and even nipples. While the overall proportions are similar, the faces are much more individualised, both in their general contours and in specific features (eyes with drooping or raised outer edges, small lower lips, curvature of the eyebrows). Such differences point to the division of labour in a sculpture workshop, with faces receiving the highest artistic attention. However, these individualised features are executed in a common manner, with eyebrows thick and distinctively curved, eyelids finely rimmed and eyes marked by incisions, thus indicating that the sculptures are contemporaneous. The variation extends to secondary elements such as cushion designs.

Fig. 1. Tīrthaṅkara, Dhar Museum no. 718.

Fig. 2. Tīrthaṅkara, Dhar Museum no. 720.

³ The sculpture is discussed in Levillain 2021 with a fresh reading of its inscription in Willis 2011: 35 and Willis 2012: 147.

Fig. 3. Padmaprabha, Dhar Museum no. 719.

On **fig. 3**, a label inscription on the pedestal identifies the image as Padmaprabha, the 6th tīrthaṅkara:

śrīpadmaprabhadevaḥ॥

The palaeography of upright nāgarī characters with sharply angled tails and wedge-like head marks suggests a date in the late-10th/early-11th century on comparison with the copper-plate charters from Ujjain (980), Gaonri (981, 986), Betma (1020), Banswada (1020) and Ujjain (1021) issued by Vākpati (c. 973-995) and Bhoja (c. 1010–1055).⁴

⁴ Trivedi 1978, nos. 5, 6-7, 10-12. Palaeographic charts are given in Singh 2012: 112-114.

Two Digambara Statues from Dhar

Similar in overall appearance to the three previously described, this marble statue likely belongs to a Digambar milieu as the figure is devoid of a loincloth (**fig. 4**). Hair curls falling on the shoulders are characteristic of Ādinātha, although the absence of a bull emblem makes this identification tentative. The angular cushion is engraved on the front with facing hamsas in the centre flanked by a donor figure and spiralling scrolls at the corners. Near the feet is a partly damaged one-line inscription of homage.

Like the previous statue, this fragmentary image of dark sandstone shows a tīrthānkara seated without a loincloth suggesting a Digambara denomination (**fig. 5**).⁵ The angular cushion is similarly subdivided into compartments, engraved with a rhomboid jewel in the centre and on the corners. A dedicatory inscription in the spaces flanking the central jewel records the tutelage of a teacher from the Lāṭavāgaḍa community of Digambaras in western India and the patronage of a merchant from the Garddabherīya lineage, otherwise unknown. The upright nāgarī letters retain a rounded aspect typical of the first half of the 11th century, indicating the likely date of the statue.⁶

Fig. 4. Tīrthānkara, Dhar, 111 × 85 cm, Dhar Museum no. 72.

Fig. 5. Śīṭalanātha (?), Dhar, Dhar Museum no. —

⁵ Lele 1944: 97 identifies it as Śīṭalanātha and gives a reading of the inscription, noticed in ARIE 1964-65, C2049 and ARIE 1976-77, C4232-33.

⁶ Compare the Betma (1020), Banswada (1020) and Ujjain (1021) copper-plates and Ambikā statue (1034) from Bhoja's reign in Trivedi 1978, pls. XII-XIV, XVIa.

Text

[¹]śrīlāṭavāgaṭasaṃghe [²]paṃḍitācārya śrīsaka[³]lacamdrāḥ||

[⁴]śrīgarddabherīya śreṣṭhi [⁵]cāhīlasuta jeḷā[⁶]ka praṇamati nityaṃ

Translation

In the illustrious Lāṭavāgaḍa community (*saṅgha*), there is the learned teacher (*paṇḍitācārya*) Sakalacandra. Jeḷāka, the son of the merchant (*śreṣṭhi*) Cāhīla of the illustrious Garddabherīya lineage bows down eternally.

Digambara Statues of the 13th Century

This is the lower part of a black stone statue showing a seated tīrthāṅkara, its pedestal engraved with the bull emblem of Ādinātha and an inscription dated 1239 (**fig. 6**).⁷

Text

[¹][saṃvat] 1295 varṣe jyeṣṭha sudi 7 gurau śrīman māthurasamghe ācārya dharmmakīrti...

[²]...bhāryā sāvitri tayo (satva)...

Translation

In the year 1295, on Thursday, the 7th of the bright fortnight of the month of Jyeṣṭha (12 May 1239), the teacher (*ācārya*) Dharmakīrti in the illustrious Māthura community (*saṅgha*)⁸... wife Sāvitri...

Fig. 6. Ādinātha (bull), Dhar, 1239, 20 × 45 cm, Dhar Museum no. 603.

⁷ All dates have been calculated through <https://hic.efeo.fr/>, an online application of the École française d'Extrême-Orient developed under supervision of Arlo Griffiths by L. Gislén, J. C. Eade and Toni Kustiana.

⁸ See Lodha 1995: 27, no. 7 for *ācārya* Dharmakīrti of Māthurasamghe in an inscription dated 1171-72 (saṃvat 1228) on a tīrthāṅkara statue from Badnawar now in the Ujjain museum of the Digambara Jaina saṃsthāna.

Fig. 7. Śāntinātha (antelope), Salkanpur, 1243. Mandu state museum no. 28.

This headless statue of a seated tirthankara is engraved on its pedestal with the antelope emblem of Śāntinātha and an inscription dated 1243 (fig. 7). It is unusual for its polished green stone and high-quality modelling in a period generally associated with a decline in refinement. Despite a progressive simplification of forms, it is comparable to older 11th-century sculpture. Certain areas of the torso are rendered in a more stylised manner, such as the curved line marking the lower contour of the pectorals. But the lower abdomen conveys volume through gradual relief rather than schematic lines common to 13th-century images. Similarly, the feet and hands have exaggerated proportions characteristic of 13th-century images, regardless of their quality of execution and their desire to maintain ancient models.

Text⁹

[¹]siddham*||saṃvat 1299 varṣe caitra sudi 6 sanau punarvvasanakṣatre|bāgaḍasaṃghe porapāṭānvayai sā° jalhaṇaputra sā°

[²]rāsala| bhāryā rattanā| putra khemadhara putra °āsadhara samastasukuṭaṃ (paṃ°) sahittāṃ| śrī śāṃtinā-

[³]thadevapratiṃ (sthā)pitā nityaṃ praṇamati||cha||cha|| maṅgalaṃ mahāśrī śubhaṃ bhavatu||

Translation

Success! In the year 1299, on Saturday, the 6th of the bright fortnight of Caitra (28 March 1243), under the constellation Punarvasu, within the Bāgaḍa community (*saṅgha*) and the Porapāṭa lineage (*anvaya*), *sādhu* Jalhaṇa's son *sādhu* Rāsala, [his] wife Ratnā, [their] son Khemadhara, [his] son Āśadhara, along with the entire family and [their] *paṇḍita*, [this] image of the illustrious lord Śāntinātha was installed. [They] bow down [to it] in eternal reverence. May there be auspiciousness, great fortune, and well-being.

This remarkably intact sandstone image shows a tīrthaṅkara seated on an ornate cushion decorated like the older images but dated by inscription to 1243 (**fig. 8**). Engraved between the folded feet of the deity, on the upper part of the pedestal, the dedicatory text itself serves as an offering of homage. It records the tutelage of a teacher from the Digambara sect Mūlasaṅgha and the collective patronage of a family belonging to a lineage from Chittor, Rajasthan. The figure displays simplified volumes and stereotyped features with a broad face and a heavy jawline. The stylised hairline on the forehead is rendered with a simple, slightly curved line. The hands and feet are long, massive and somewhat flat. Interestingly, a conch in the centre of the cushion

Fig. 8. Neminātha (conch), Mandu, ASI Museum.

helps identify the tīrthaṅkara as Neminātha, but the hair curls falling on the shoulders would suggest it to be an image of Ādinātha. It is possible that in the 13th century, an attribute used to distinguish the first tīrthaṅkara became a standard feature in the representation of tīrthaṅkaras more generally. The damaged heads of 13th-century images preclude verification of this hypothesis and it remains difficult to determine whether elements projecting from the shoulders of images dated 1251 are strands of hair or parts of distended earlobes.

⁹ Noticed in ARIE 1988-89, B76.

Text

[1]saṃ 1299 varṣe jyeṣṭha su 13 some

[2]śrīmūlasaṃghe ācāryaśrī(kīrttiśema)saca(bheju)

[3]citrakūṭānvaye sã° dāhaḍa bhārjā sobhī putra līhā bhārjā yāmiṇi

[4]bhrātri ṣemaṃdhara bhārjā padamā putra mahādeva pūnāharadeva mahādeva ete praṇamati nityaṃ

Translation

In the year 1299, on Monday, the 13th of the bright fortnight of the month of Jyeṣṭha (1 June 1243), the teacher (*ācārya*)...in the illustrious Mūla community (*saṅgha*) and Citrakūṭa lineage (*anvaya*), *sādhu* Dāhaḍa, his wife Sobhī, [their] son Līhā, [his] wife Yāmiṇi, [her] brother Khemadhara, [his] wife Padamā, [and their] sons Mahādeva, Pūnāharadeva and Mahādeva, bow down in eternal reverence.

Dark stone sculpture of a tīrthaṅkara (identified as Śāntinātha by Lele 1944) standing upright in *kayotsarga*, flanked by two attendants with flywhisks (**fig. 9**). The stepped base below the feet is inscribed with a yantra of seed syllables in an eight-petalled yantra. A dedicatory inscription refers to the Digambara sect Māthurasaṅgha and the lineage Vardhamānapurānvaya, after the city of Badnawar, 50 km north of Dhar, where a number of statues were commissioned by members of the same lineage. An image inscription from Badnawar dated saṃvat 1308 suggests a possible date for this statue from Dhar.¹⁰ The thick, massive body has schematically rendered volumes, with neck folds and lower abdomen marked by incised lines. The facial features are disproportionate with large cheeks distancing

¹⁰ See Lodha 1995, no. 3, 6, 7 for images dated saṃvat 1210, 1226, 1236.

Fig. 9. Śāntinātha (?), Dhar, c. 1250, Dhar Museum no. 85.

the eyes from the mouth. The attendants have fairly flat volumes covered with ornaments that liken them to figures flanking door guardians of temples in the 12th-13th centuries.

Text¹¹ reads continuously top-down on each projecting surface from left to right.

Left: ^[1]māgha vadi 5 māthurā^[2]nvaye paṇḍita śrī cchatra^[3]sena tacchiṣya padmase^[4] _

Centre: ^[1][va](rddha)mānapurānvaye śreṣṭhi vasamtarāja tatputra sādhu nārāyaṇa sa ^[2]dhadevaḥ nārāyaṇa suta āsadhara la(kṣmī)^[3]dhara vaccharāja praṇamati nityaṃ^[4][ya]sakīrtiḥ śreṣṭhiṇi haṃṣasi praṇamati

Right: ^[1]tathā paṇḍita śrī ama(ra)^[2]va tacchiṣya paṇḍitācārya ^[3]śrītrāṣṭeṇā tacchiṣya paṇ ^[4]ācārya mādhavacaṃdro

Translation¹²

(In the year...), on Tuesday, the 5th of the dark fortnight in the month of Māgha, in the Māthura lineage are the venerable teacher (*paṇḍita*) Chattrasena and his disciple (*śiṣya*) Padmasena. In the lineage of the city Vardhamānapura, the merchant (*śreṣṭhi*) Vasamtarāja, [his] son the merchant (*sādhu*) Nārāyaṇa and Sadhadeva, Nārāyaṇa's sons Āsadhara, Lakṣmīdhara, and Vaccharāja bow down perpetually. Yaśakīrti and the merchant-woman (*śreṣṭhiṇi*) Haṃṣasi likewise bow down; also the scholar (*paṇḍita*) Amara and his disciple the venerable scholar-teacher (*paṇḍitācārya*) Trāṣṭeṇā and his disciple the scholar-teacher (*paṇḍitācārya*) Mādhavacandra.

¹¹ Lele 1944, 95-96; ARIE 1964-65, 125, C2050.

¹² The year may have been given on the now-broken flank of the pedestal to the left.

Ten statues from Salkanpur dated 1251

A group of ten marble statues from Salkanpur bear inscriptions recording their consecration on the same day in the year 1251 (figs. 10-19). Shown seated in *padmāsana*, the tīrthaṅkaras are identical in all respects and identifiable only by the emblems carved in the centre of the decorated cushion, whose upper surface is engraved with the dedicatory text set out before the Jina's feet. Following the same epigraphic format, the texts record names of merchants from the Prāgvāta clan (*anvaya*) belonging to the Lāṭavāgaḍa community (*saṅgha*) of Digambaras, so named after the historical regions of Lāṭa and Vāgaḍa situated in southeastern Gujarat and Rajasthan respectively.¹³ The sculptures are distinguished by exaggerated bodily proportions, with large hands and feet, stunted torso with broad shoulders on a much narrower waist. The bold decoration of nipples and pectoral ornament, a navel marked by compass lines, and an angular cushion with ornaments in compartments conveys an aesthetic of sharp contrasts. Palaeographically, the nāgarī letters show a bold, rectilinear form useful for establishing chronological brackets for undated sculptures.

Fig. 10. Tīrthaṅkara, Dhar Museum no. 31.

Fig. 11. Neminātha (conch), Dhar Museum no. 32.

Text (fig. 10)

^[1]saṃvat 1307 varṣe jeṣṭha-vadi 11 guraū paurapāṭā^[2]nve sā°bhāvaḍa bhāryā sājaṇi praṇamati nityaṃ||

Translation

In the year 1307, on Thursday, the 11th of the dark fortnight in the month of Jyeṣṭha (15 June 1251), in the Paurapāṭa lineage, the merchant (*sadhu*) Bhāvaḍa and [his] wife Sājaṇi bow down perpetually.

Text (fig. 11)

^[1]saṃvat 1306 varṣe jeṣṭha-vadi 11 guraū śrīlā^[2]ṭavāgaḍasaṃghe prāguvāṭānvaye sā°rāya bhāryā kelū suta jāhaḍa^[3]bhāryā pī(gh)ū suta bhānū bhāryā nākra bhrāṭṛ dhīradeva bhāryā śīci... bhrāṭṛ mahādeva bhāryā mahāśrī^[4]suta...ṣābhūvā ...ti(ja)pada(sā°)^[5]...praṇamati nityaṃ||

¹³ Johrapurkar 1958: 248-262 gives an overview of the Lāṭavāgaḍa-gaccha of the Kāṣṭhāsaṅgha.

Fig. 12. Tirthankara, Dhar Museum no. 33.

Fig. 13. Mahāvīra (lion), Dhar Museum no. 34.

Translation

In the year 1306,¹⁴ on Thursday, 11th of the dark fortnight of the month of Jyeṣṭha (15 June 1251), in the Lāṭavāgaḍa community and the Prāguvāṭa lineage, the merchant (*sadhu*) Rāya, [his] wife Kelu, [their] son Jāhaḍa, [his] wife Pīghū, [their] son Bhānu, [his] wife Nākra, [her] brother Dhīradeva, [his] wife Khīci, [her] brother Mahādeva, [his] wife Mahāśrī, [their] son - ... khābhūvā....bow down perpetually.

Text (fig. 12)

^[1]saṃvat 1307 varṣe jyeṣṭha-vadi 11 gurau śrīlāḍavāgaḍā^[2]nvaye paṇḍita śrīmadanakīrtti paurapāṭānvaye ye sā°vādula bhāryā pupūniṇi ^[3]suta va°ijā patnī jadhaṃsiri guṇasiri suta nāgadeva somadeva āgadatapāladeva praṇamati.

Translation

In the year 1307, on Thursday, the 11th of the dark fortnight of the month of Jyeṣṭha (15 June 1251), in the Lāṭavāgaḍa community the venerable scholar (*paṇḍita*) Madanakīrtti and in the Paurapāṭa lineage, the merchant (*sadhu*) Vādula, [his] wife Pupūniṇi, [their] son Vaijā, [his] wife Jadhaṃsiri, [her husband] Guṇasiri, [their] sons Nāgadeva, Somadeva, and Āgadatapāladeva bow down perpetually.

Text (fig. 13)

^[1]saṃvat 1307 varṣe jyeṣṭha-vadi 11 gurau ^[2]lāṭavāgaḍānvaye ratnakīrtti paurapāṭānvaye sā°rāsala suta ^[3]ṣisudhā bhāryā jāsū putra °āsādhara lihū putra dhaṇadeva praṇamati nityaṃ

Translation

In the year 1307, on Thursday, 11th of the dark fortnight of Jyeṣṭha (15 June 1251), in the Lāṭavāgaḍa community Ratnakīrtti and in the Paurapāṭa lineage, the merchant (*sadhu*) Rāsala, [his] son Khisudhā, [his] wife Jāsu, [their] son Āsādhara, [his] wife Lihū and [their] son Dhaṇadeva bow down perpetually.

¹⁴ This appears to be an error for 1307, as the rest of the date is identical to that in the nine other statues and also matches the weekday.

Fig. 14. Ajitanātha (elephant), Dhar Museum no. 35.

Fig. 15. Sambhavanātha (elephant), Dhar Museum no. 36.

Text (fig. 14)

^[1]saṃvat 1307 varṣe jyeṣṭha-vadi 11 gurau lāṭavāga ^[2]ḍasaṃghe pāurapāṭānvaye sã°dūlahadhāmsū suta māḍaṇa lāḍaṇa ^[3]ratana praṇamati nityaṃ||

Translation

In the year 1307, on Thursday, the 11th of the dark fortnight in the month of Jyeṣṭha (15 June 1251), in the Lāṭavāgaḍa community and the Paurapāṭa lineage, the merchant (*sādhu*) Dūlahadhāmsū and [his] sons Māḍaṇa, Lāḍaṇa and Ratana bow down perpetually.

Text (fig. 15)

^[1]saṃvat 1307 varṣe jaiṣṭha-vadi 11 gurau lāṭavāgaḍasaṃghe paurapāṭā ^[2]nvaye sã°rāsala suta_ _dhara bhāryā haje putra āsādhara bhāryā līhū putra dhaṇā ^[3]_ _ praṇamati nityaṃ||

Translation

In the year 1307, on Thursday, 11th of the dark fortnight in the month of Jyeṣṭha (15 June 1251), in the Paurapāṭa lineage of the Lāṭavāgaḍa sect, the merchant (*sādhu*) Rāsala, [his] son –dhara, [his] wife Haje, [their] son Āsādhara, [his] wife Līhū and [their] son Dhaṇā bow down perpetually.

Text (fig. 16)

^[1]saṃvat 1307 jyeṣṭha-vadi 11 gurau lāṭavāgaḍa ^[2]nvaye pāurapāṭānvaye sã°vaijā putra somadeva bhāryā ^[3]salaṣū putra haradeva dhīradeva putrī lāha ^[4]praṇamati nityaṃ||

Translation

In the year 1307, on Thursday, the 11th of the dark fortnight in the month of Jyeṣṭha (15 June 1251), in the Lāṭavāgaḍa community and the Paurapāṭa lineage, the merchant (*sādhu*) Vaijā, [his] son Somadeva, [his] wife Salakhū, [their] sons Haradeva, Dhīradeva and daughter Lāha bow down perpetually.

Fig. 16. Mahāvīra (lion), Dhar Museum no. 37.

Fig. 17. Tīrthankara, Dhar Museum no. 38.

Text (fig. 17)

^[1]saṃvat 1307 varṣe jyeṣṭha-vadi 11 gurau śrīlāḍavāgaḍānvaye paṃ^o mada^[2]nakīrttiḥ prāgvātānvaye sā^ovāijā putra nāgadevā bhāryā vīlū putra śāma^[3]deva somadevaḥ putrī mā^oide^oi praṇamati nityaṃḥ

Translation

In the year 1307, on Thursday, the 11th of the dark fortnight in the month of Jyeṣṭha (15 June 1251), in the Lāṭavāgaḍa sect the scholar (*paṇḍita*) Madanakīrtti and in the Paurapāṭa lineage, the merchant (*sādhu*) Vāijā, [his] son Nāgadeva, [his] wife Vīlū, [their] sons Śāmadeva and Somadeva, [his] daughter Māidevī bow down perpetually.

Text (fig. 18)

^[1]saṃvat 1307 varṣe jyeṣṭha-vadi 11 gurau ^[2]lāṭa-vāgaḍasaṃghe paurapāṭānvaye sā^oghailā suta (sy)āmadeva bhā^[3]ryā ... praṇa[mati nityaṃḥ]

Translation

In the year 1307, on Thursday, the 11th of the dark fortnight in the month of Jyeṣṭha (15 June 1251), in the Lāṭavāgaḍa community and the Paurapāṭa lineage, the merchant (*sādhu*) Ghailā, [his] son Śyāmadeva, [his] wife ... bow down perpetually.

Text (fig. 19)

^[1]saṃvat 1307 varṣe jyeṣṭhavadi 11 gurau ^[2]lāṭavāgaḍasaṃghe śrīprāgvātānvaye sā^o ...

^[3]...sāya bhāryā vāchiṇi suta bhrāṭṛ arjuna

^[4]...bhārya _ _ _ti putra bhajadeva ca tīna praṇamati nityaṃḥ

^[5]... (hālaṇa) _ _ _ praṇamati

Translation

In the year 1307, on Thursday, 11th of the dark fortnight in the month of Jyeṣṭha (15 June 1251), in the Lāṭavāgaḍa community and the Prāgvāṭa lineage, the merchant (*sādhu*)[his] wife Vāchiṇi, [her] brother's son Arjuna .. bow down perpetually.

Fig. 18. Abhinandanātha (monkey), Mandu state museum no. 27.

Fig. 19. Ajitanātha (elephant), Mandu state museum no. 29.

Three image pedestals of 13th-century Dhar

Text (fig. 20)

^[1][saṃvat 13]23 varṣe māghasudi 7 some| śrīmūlasaṃghaseṇasaṃghe| ācāryāśrīdurllabhasena| khaṇḍellavālānvaye|| sādhu-guṇadā| suta-sādhu-jāhaḍa ^[2][bhāryā]...si tathā suta sādhu-(āṃgā) bhāryā-ratanā| suta sādhu-āsā bhāryā kajū| tathā sādhu-salaṣaṇa bhāryā-jasadevi| putra-ka(mala) ^[3]ebhi ātmaśreyorthaṃ śrīmunisuvratadevapatimā pratiṣṭhāpya praṇamati nityaṃ||cha||

Translation

In the year 1323, on Monday, the 7th of the bright fortnight in the month of Māgha (23 January 1268), in the illustrious Mūla and Seṇa communities (*saṅgha*) is the teacher (*ācārya*) Durlabhasena. In the Khaṇḍelavāla lineage is the merchant (*sādhu*) Guṇadā; [his] sons *sādhu* Jāhaḍa [with wife...] and *sādhu* āṃgā [with] wife Ratanā; [their] son *sādhu* Āśā [with] wife Kajū; and *sādhu* Salakhaṇa [with] wife Jasadevī; [their] son Kamala. These individuals, for the sake of their own spiritual welfare, the statue of the illustrious lord Munisuvrata was consecrated. They bow down [to it] in perpetual reverence. Auspiciousness!

Fig. 20. Munisuvrata (tortoise), Dhar, 1268, Dhar Museum no. 2577.

Black stone statue of the seated tīrthaṅkara Ādinātha identified by a bull emblem engraved on the pedestal and dated by a long dedicatory inscription that replaces the decorated cushion (fig. 21).

Text

^[1]|| saṃ° 1331 varṣe jeṣṭṭha sūdi 6 budhe śrīmūlasaṃghe seṇasaṃghe śrīdevendrasenatanu
siddhabhaṭṭāraka-śrījasobhadradeva||^[2]||dhākaḍānvaye sā°(mā)lha bhāryā-sobhā tatputra sā°vīsala
bhāryā-salagna tasuputra sā°lāvaṇa bhāryā-delhū bha(nu) putra (priyā) ^[3]sā°lāṣaṇa bhāryā-(sājha)
tatputra māhadeva-sahadeva (reva)sīlī (svadeṣa)|| sā°lāṣaṇa bhāryā-vaccha tasuputra kāmadeva
dharmadeva ^[4]ābhā āmadevadho mohaṇi putra-ratna| sā°dāmara suta śrī- _ dā _ _ (śiṣya) sā°
rāmadeva suta padma praṇamati nityaṃ|| śrī subhaṃ (bha)vatu

Translation

In the year 1331, on Wednesday, the 6th of the bright fortnight in the month of Jyeṣṭha (1 May 1275), in the venerable Mūlasaṅgha and Senasaṅgha is the perfected pontiff (*bhaṭṭāraka*), the venerable Jasobhadra, son of the venerable Devendrasena. In the Dhākaḍa clan is the merchant (*sādhu*) Mālha and wife Sobhā, [their] son *sādhu* Vīsala and wife Salagna, [their] son *sādhu* Lāvaṇa and [his] wife Delhū, [their] son..., *sādhu* Lākhaṇa and [his] wife Sājha, [their] sons Māhadeva and Sahadeva, and [relatives] Revasīlī and Svadeṣa; *sādhu* Lākhaṇa and [his] wife Vāccha, [their] son Kāmadeva; Dharmadeva and Ābhā; Āmadeva and Mohaṇi, [their] son Ratna. *sādhu* Dāmara, [his] son..., his (disciple) *sādhu* Rāmadeva, his son Padma – bow down perpetually. May it be auspicious!

Fig. 21. Ādinātha (bull), Dhar, 1275, Dhar Museum no. 69.

Text (fig. 22)

[¹] [saṃvat ...6] varṣe māgha sudi 13 ravau mūlasaṅghe deśīgaṇānvaye...siṣya

[²] ...siṣyā paṇḍitācārya ...paṇḍitasya siṣya dharmemdra caṃdrasya (sijikā āśrama) śrī praṇamati nityaṃ

Translation

In the year ..., on Sunday, the 13th of the bright fortnight in the month of Māgha, in the Mūlasaṅgha and Deśīgaṇā lineage, ... [his] disciple... [his] disciple the learned teacher (*paṇḍitācārya*) ... his disciple (*siṣya*) Dharmendra and Candra bow down perpetually.

Fig. 22. Tirthāṅkara, Dhar, Dhar Museum no. 788.

Conclusion

The Jain statues presented here belong to two distinct phases of artistic production in the Paramāra kingdom of Malwa, based on stylistic analysis and reading of the inscriptions. Dateable to the first half of the 11th century, the first three marble statues are distinguished by smooth forms and allusive volumes, rendered delicately despite the angularity inherent in Jain aesthetics. Lacking dedicatory inscriptions, their importance lies as much in the confidence of the forms as in their discreet individuality. To these Śvetāmbara statues can be added two Digambara images of Ādinātha and Śītanātha, whose torsos and cushion designs are comparable, with the latter bearing an inscription in 11th-century characters. By contrast, the seventeen statues dated in the 13th century attest to a flourishing production in series, distinguished by reduced size and quality of anatomical volumes but increased ornamentation and stylisation. An important outlier is the green stone Śāntinātha dated 1243, distinct from the decorative aesthetic of contrasts found in the 13th-century Jain repertoire, where sobriety nonetheless reigns supreme.

Long inscriptions commemorating communal devotion assume greater significance in the 13th century. Following a formulaic structure, they typically provide the date of consecration, the name of the Jain community (*saṅgha*), branch (*gaṇa*) or lineage (*anvaya*) of the religious preceptors, followed by the lineage of the donors whose names are set forth in sequential family relationships, closing with a collective act of eternal homage (*praṇamati nityam*). The eleven

Salkanpur statues record activity of Digambaras from the Prāgvāṭa (Pāurapāṭa/ Poravāṭa) caste affiliated to the Lāṭa-Vāgaḍa branch active in southeastern Gujarat and Rajasthan. It is noteworthy that the epigraphic usage was rather indifferent to the technical difference between the terms *saṅgha*, *gaṇa* and *anvaya* indicating various subdivisions of the Digambara tradition.¹⁵ Three images refer to the Mūla- and Seṇa-saṅghas, while two others to the Māthurasaṅgha, thus adding important information to the history of medieval Jainism in 13th-century Malwa.

This epigraphic data may be relevant for understanding the sourcing of materials. For the conspicuous use of white marble in a region where sandstone was the prevalent medium raises the problem of provenance. While streaked marble in the 11th-century statues could be sourced from local quarries in the Vindhyan range, the clear crystalline marble of the ten images dated 1251 is usually associated with the Makrana region of Rajasthan.¹⁶ Pending petrographic analysis, prosopographic data may shed light on the role of Prāgvāṭa lineages of the Lāṭa-Vāgaḍa branch in the transport of high-quality stone to Malwa. Although limited, the corpus thus provides important evidence for artistic activity and religious community under the later Paramāras, raising questions about how workshop production was organised, with sculptures made-to-order or made-to-stock, and how Jain families inscribed their presence through pious acts of patronage prompted by their lineage preceptors. It is hoped that this sculptural sequence, while adding to the existing corpus from Malwa, can eventually pave the way for a fuller assessment of Jain statuary through the publication of such assemblages from Madhya Pradesh.¹⁷

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¹⁵ See Detige 2020: 187.

¹⁶ Krishnan et al. 1965, 16 reports mottled and streaked marble from quarries in Raisen district.

¹⁷ Lodha 1995: 62-63, nos. 214–219 reporting only six images from Dhar.

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